

Oedera humilis Perdekaroo

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.3 - 1 meters (height)

Distribution:

Oedera humilis is widespread throughout the arid areas of southern Africa and occurs in southern and southwestern Botswana, southern Namibia, and the karoo areas of the Cape and the southern Free State.

Importance:

This species is one of the bushes recognized in the Government Gazette No. 49556 as an essential part of the sheep diet required for producing certified Karoo lamb. Highly drought-resistant, it plays a critical role as forage during dry periods when most other plants have been grazed, even though it is not particularly palatable. Its new growth, however, carries a pleasantly aromatic flavour.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 176.7 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.12 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 4.54 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 3.5%, Duplicated: 96.0%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 87 919.35 kilobases

Contig number: 1 254

Sample Contributor contact details:

Renée Prins

CenGen

cengen@cengen.co.za

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